
THE EFFECT OF LEARNING ENTREPRENEURSHIP TOWARDS STUDENT MOTIVATION OF STIE YPBI JAKARTA

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Abstract:

Indonesia's development requires educated, skilled, innovative, independent souls, physically and mentally healthy. Entrepreneurship education is very important to be taught to students so that after finishing college they can create jobs instead of looking for work.

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of learning Entrepreneurship courses on student entrepreneurial motivation. Entrepreneurship is a mental and mental attitude that is always active in trying to advance its devotional work in an effort to increase income in its business activities. While motivation is something that encourages someone to act or behave in a certain way to meet their needs. The method used in this study is a qualitative method with a sample of 40 respondents and data collection techniques using questionnaires. The results of this study are simple linear regression analysis calculated as follows: $Y = Y' = 21.31 + 0.502 X$, the correlation coefficient (r) between the variables X and Y is obtained by the correlation coefficient of 0.70. This value indicates that the two variables have a positive and strong influence. the magnitude of the effect of learning Entrepreneurship courses on student entrepreneurial motivation is 49%, while the remaining 51% is influenced by other factors not included in this research variable. Furthermore, it is known that there is a positive and significant influence on student entrepreneurial motivation, because the value of t_{count} is greater than the value of t_{table} ($6.039 > 2.024$) then H_a is accepted.

Keywords: Learning Entrepreneurship Courses; Student Entrepreneurial Motivation.

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1. Introduction

Unemployment and poverty occur because the comparison between the number of job opportunity offers in all sectors, both at home and abroad is not proportional to the number of graduates or new job offers produced at all levels of education both at the junior secondary level to the level of universities.

The orientation of education graduates, including tertiary institutions, is only to find work, not create jobs, apparently these ideals have been going on for a long time in Indonesia, so it is not surprising that every year the number of unemployed people continues to grow, while employment growth is narrower.

Meanwhile, the government is not very responsive to change the mindset of the community, even if there are only a small number beginning in the 2000s, entrepreneurial activities are initiated by the government through entering entrepreneurship courses in universities that are expected to create entrepreneurial spirits so that they can stand alone and create work that continues to increase every year. Entrepreneurship education in Indonesia lags far behind that of other countries, where in other countries it began in the 1970s while in Indonesia it only began in the 1990s, besides that we need to be concerned about the low interest of students and youth to become entrepreneurs and they want to become civil servants or work in companies big. To become an entrepreneur there is no strong encouragement from the family where parents want their children to become civil servants and work in large companies both at home and abroad. Motivation of students or young people to become entrepreneurs is still low and feels embarrassed, also they reason to become entrepreneurs need capital so they discourage them from becoming entrepreneurs. For that, according to STIE YPBI's motto, before graduating, after working as an entrepreneur, to equip students to become entrepreneurs in the future, at STIE YPBI students are given entrepreneurship courses 1 and 2 and there are business laboratories and business practices. In addition, there are also students who have opened a business, this is very relevant to produce young entrepreneurs who are not dependent on looking for work but opening their own jobs and being able to absorb workers as employees, also helping government programs to reduce educated unemployment.

2. Literature Review

Understanding Learning

According to Udin S Winataputra (2008: 14) learning is defined as the process of gaining knowledge by reading and using experience as knowledge that guides behavior in the future. This is in line with the constructivist theory of learning which emphasizes the process more than the results. Learning is the process of building or forming meaning, knowledge, concepts and ideas through experience.

Understanding Entrepreneurship

According to Dan Steinhoff and John F. Burgess (1993: 35) entrepreneurs are people who organize, manage and dare to bear the risk of creating new businesses and business opportunities. Essentially the notion of entrepreneurship is a mental attitude, outlook, insight and mindset and pattern of one's actions towards task duties that are their responsibility and are always customer-oriented. Or it can also be interpreted as all the actions of someone who is able to give value to their duties and responsibilities. Entrepreneurship is a mental and mental attitude that is always active in trying to advance its devotional work in an effort to increase income in its business activities. In addition, entrepreneurship is a creative and innovative ability that is used as a basis, tips and resources to find opportunities for success.

Entrepreneurship is the spirit, attitude, behavior and ability of a person to handle a business or activity that leads to efforts to find, create, implement work methods, technology and new products by increasing efficiency in order to provide better services and or gain greater profits. Entrepreneurship is the process of creating something else by using time and activities along with service capital and risk, and receiving remuneration, satisfaction, and personal freedom. Entrepreneurship Benefits From a number of studies, it has been intensified that micro business owners, small, or believe that they tend to work harder, make more money, and are more

proud than working in a large company. Before starting a business, every prospective entrepreneur should consider the benefits of having a micro, small or medium business. Thomas W Zimmerer et al. (2005) formulating entrepreneurial benefits are as follows: 1. Giving opportunities and freedom to control one's own destiny owning a business will provide freedom and opportunity for business people to achieve their life goals. Businessmen will try Win their lives and enable them to use their business to realize their dreams. 2. Give opportunities to make changes More and more businesses are starting their businesses because they can capture opportunities to make changes that they think are very important. Perhaps in the form of providing simple, healthy and suitable housing, and establishing waste recycling to preserve limited natural resources, business people are now finding ways to combine their manifestations of concern for various economic and social issues in the hope of living a better life. 3. Providing opportunities to achieve full potential, many people realize that working in a company is often boring, less challenging and no attraction. This certainly does not apply to an entrepreneur, for them there is not much difference between working or distributing hobbies or playing, both are the same. The business owned by entrepreneurs is a tool for expressing self-actualization. Their success is something that is determined by creativity, enthusiasm, innovation, and their own vision. Owning a business or the company itself gives them power, spiritual awakening and is able to follow their own interests or hobbies. 4. Have the opportunity to profit. Even though in the initial stages of money is not the main attraction for entrepreneurs, the benefits of entrepreneurship are an important motivating factor for establishing their own business, most business people do not want to be rich, but most of those who win become wealthy. Nearly 75% of those included in the list of richest people (Forbes Magazine) are first generation entrepreneurs. According to the results of the study, Thomas Stanley and William Danko, the owners of the company themselves reached 2/3 of the American millionaires. "People who work with their own companies are four times more likely to become millionaires than people who work for other people (other company employees). 5. Have the opportunity to play an active role in the community and get recognition for their efforts Entrepreneurs or small business owners are often the most respected and trusted citizens. Business agreements based on trust and mutual respect are the characteristics of small entrepreneurs. Owners like trust and recognition received from customers who have been served faithfully for many years. The important role played in business systems in the local environment as well as the awareness that work has a real impact in carrying out the national social and economic functions is a reward for small company managers. 6. Have the opportunity to do something that is liked and foster a sense of pleasure in doing it. The thing that is based on small entrepreneurs or small business owners is that their business activities are not really work. Most entrepreneurs who succeed in choosing to enter a particular business, because they are interested and like the job. They channel their hobbies or hobbies into their jobs and they are happy that they do it. Entrepreneurs must follow the advice of Harvey McKey. According to McKey: "Look for and establish a business that you like and you will not be forced to work even a day in your life." This is the biggest appreciation for business people / entrepreneurs not the purpose, but rather the process or journey.

Entrepreneurial Function

Basically, humans need food, drink, clothing, and so on. That need will increase along with the progress of the times which leads humans to carry out consumptive activities. Unemployment that is increasing if not addressed will make humans potentially negative. Therefore, an entrepreneurial spirit is needed for every human being so as to reduce the number of unemployed people.

Every Entrepreneur has additional functions and functions as follows:

- 1) The main functions of entrepreneurship are: Making important decisions and taking risks about the company's goals and objectives, deciding the company's goals and objectives. Establish the business sector and the market to be served, calculate the scale of business he wants, determine the desired capital (own capital or capital from outside). choosing and establishing employee / employee criteria and motivating them, controlling effectively and efficiently, seeking and creating new ways, looking for new breakthroughs in getting input or input and managing them into attractive goods or services, marketing those goods and services to satisfy customers and at the same time can obtain and maintain maximum profits.
- 2) Additional functions of entrepreneurship, namely: Recognizing the company's environment in order to find and create business opportunities, Control the environment in a direction that is profitable for the company, maintain the business environment so as not to harm the community due to the business waste that might result, spend and care about CSR. Every entrepreneur must care and take responsibility for the environment

Principles of Entrepreneurship

The most important entrepreneurial principles are brave or out of fear of failure, bold meaning here is an action where we must be able to take a stand on the opportunities that arise in life, especially the opportunity to set up a business. An entrepreneur knows no level of education but knows at the level of someone daring to take Resiko. Though education is important but its role here is precisely at the level of courage for the effort we will make. Education here is useful at the level of expertise of the business field that we will establish but it is not a basic principle in building a business, but it is our courage that can be a basic principle in building a business.

Besides that, to be entrepreneurs, we are also required to think optimistically about the opportunities and efforts we make, because then our enthusiasm and strong will and perseverance will create our business that is progressing and developing. Also, besides that we must think of alternatives where alternative thinking we create an idea and strategy from and for the effort we will do for our business.

The principles of entrepreneurship according to Dhidiek D. Machyudin, namely: Must be optimistic, ambitious, can read market opportunities, Patience, Don't despair, Don't be afraid of failure. The first and second failures are normal, suppose failure is delayed success There is also the principle of entrepreneurship expressed by KhafidhulUlum. There are seven principles given, including: Passion (spirit), Independent (self), Marketing sensitivity (sensitive to the market), Creative and innovative (creative and innovative), Calculated risk taker (taking risks with calculation), Persistent (never giving up), High ethical standards (based on ethical standards). So, if the two opinions are combined there are 12 principles in entrepreneurship, namely: Don't be afraid of failure. energetic, creative and innovative, acting calculated in taking risks. patient, resilient and diligent, must be optimistic, Abisius, never give up or do not despair, sensitive to the market or can read market opportunities. do business with ethical standards, independently. Honest. Care about the environment.

Understanding Entrepreneurial Motivation

Motivation is something that encourages someone to act or behave in a certain way to meet their needs. According to Abraham Maslow motivation is classified into 5 levels, namely: 1. Physiological needs such as: eating, drinking, clothing, food, entertainment and others, 2. Security needs, namely the need for safety and protection from danger, threats, and deprivation or dismissal from work, 3. Social needs such as a sense of family, friendship, and affection, 4. Needs of appreciation such as appreciation, honor and recognition, 5. Self-actualization needs like self-expression, creativity and completing your own work.

Students are motivated to become entrepreneurs because to become successful entrepreneurs, the above needs can be fulfilled. Of course, how successful are entrepreneurs?

Entrepreneur Successful

To be a successful entrepreneur, among others: Having formal education and creative culture, a passion that is flaming, courageous and responsible, skilled in thinking and resilient in the sense that the analysis must be precise, systematic, with high ability according to the foundation of the nation's philosophy Indonesia, namely Pancasila, is able to organize itself, subordinates, and other co-workers. Able to get along and be flexible in community relations, prioritize profitable success, not consumptive, not wasteful and can save money.

A person who, in any event, is able to stand on his own ability to help himself out of the difficulties he faces. Having the maturity of perseverance is not quickly satisfied with the results achieved can juggle weaknesses into advantages attracting wisdom from failure to never give up hardiness.

Entrepreneur Excellence

- 1) Know what you want, formulate it, plan its efforts, and determine the program's deadline to achieve it.
- 2) Think carefully and have a creative outlook with constructive imagination Mentally ready to ambush and create opportunities and be ready mentally and competency readiness to meet proficiency requirements to work on something positive
- 3) Be mentally ready to ambush and create opportunities and be ready mentally and competency readiness to meet proficiency requirements to work on something positive.
- 4) Get used to being mentally positive forward and always passionate about every job.
- 5) Having self-driving power that always raises initiatives
- 6) Know to be grateful for themselves, the time, and to be grateful for their environment
- 7) Willing to pay the price of progress, namely willingness to struggle
- 8) Advancing the environment by helping others, so that others can help themselves.
- 9) Getting used to building self discipline, willing to save, and making a budget of time and money
- 10) Always draw lessons from mistakes, mistakes, bitter experiences, and concerns

To build confidence: Get to know the positive part of yourself trying to sit in front Trying to look at people's faces Walk faster Speak up Fresh smile / wide Factors that are detrimental to entrepreneurs: People who live passively and surrender to the condition of people who are weak souls Mental inferiority personality factors Habits that are not good Entrepreneurial Advantages

and Disadvantages According to Ilik (2010) there are advantages and disadvantages when someone takes the choice to become an entrepreneur, including:

Advantages:

- 1) Autonomy Management that is free and not bound makes entrepreneurship position someone to be a "boss" who has the will to control his business. This is also supported by the opinion of Robert T. Kiyosaki who stated that basically the perspective of being an entrepreneur is a choice because it seeks a freedom.
- 2) Opportunities to develop business concepts that can generate profits greatly motivate entrepreneurs.
- 3) Financial control (financial supervision). Free in managing finances, and feeling wealth as their own.
- 4) has strong moral legitimacy to realize prosperity and create employment opportunities.

3. Method of Research

This research was conducted by survey method using a questionnaire (questionnaire) as the main instrument in collecting primary data. The questionnaire consisted of open questions, in which respondents were asked to answer questions that were asked without any closed choices and questions, namely respondents could only choose from the available answer choices. Research data was qualitative. The sampling technique used was Purposive Sampling Test. Research

The population in this study were STIE YPBI Jakarta students, and the samples were all students from study programs who received Entrepreneurship courses in the even semester of 2016-2017 as many as 40 students.

4. Successful Research

Simple regression analysis is used to determine the functional relationship between variables X and variable Y. there is also a simple regression formula, $\hat{Y} = a + bx$, $n = 40$, $\sum xy = 6$, $\sum X = 1546$, $\sum X^2 = 60412$, $\sum Y = 1630$ $\sum Y^2 = 66766$, and the results are: $a = 21.31$, $b = 0.502$ $\hat{Y} = 21.31 + 0.502 X$ Can be interpreted if the brand image (X) 0.502 is ignored or not worthy, entrepreneurial motivation (Y) has a value of 21.31. Every addition of one point in learning entrepreneurship (X), it will add entrepreneurial motivation (Y) of 0.502 points. From the results of the Correlation calculation above it can be concluded that the r_{xy} Correlation Coefficient = 0.70 means that there is a strong relationship between variables X (learning entrepreneurship with variable Y ((entrepreneurial motivation) Based on the calculation above, it can be seen from the Determination Coefficient (KD) of 49%. This means that the influence of entrepreneurial learning with entrepreneurial motivation is 49%. It also states that 51% of entrepreneurial motivation is influenced by other factors not examined. from the calculation results can be known $t_{count} = 6.039$ and t_{table} is $a = 0.05$: $2 = 0.025$ with $dk = n-2 = 40-2 = 38$. So for $t_{table} 0.025 = 38$ is 2.024. then the result of t_{count} is greater than t_{table} which is $6.039 > 2.024$. If $t_{count} > t_{table}$ then H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected, which means there is an influence of variable X (learning entrepreneurship) on variable Y (entrepreneurial motivation)

5. Conclusion

- 1) Based on the results of the Linear Regression test, namely $a = 21.31$, $b = 0.502$ linear.
- 2) 2.. Based on the results of the research obtained the value of the Correlation Coefficient of 0.70. Which means that there is a strong influence between Entrepreneurship subjects and student entrepreneurial motivation
- 3) Based on the results of the study obtained the Determination Coefficient value of 0.49 which means that the contribution or contribution of Entrepreneurship subject learning to learning motivation is 49% while the remaining 51% is influenced by other variables that are beyond the scope of research.
- 4) Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the value of t count is 6.039 and t table is 2.024. because the value of $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ ($6.039 > 2.024$) it can be concluded that at the 95% confidence level there is the influence of learning Entrepreneurship courses with student entrepreneurial motivation

6. Suggestion

- 1) Each college must enter the Entrepreneurship course as a compulsory subject for students.
- 2) Students are given a view to creating jobs that are better than looking for work.
- 3) Entrepreneurship is a noble job that makes people become independent, strong, patient, diligent, tenacious and others.

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